

been assigned using molecular orbital scheme which involves equatorial bonding as suggested by Selbin⁷ and accordingly McCormick⁸ assigned the d-d absorption bands at 16 000–16 500, 17 600–18 200 and 22 500–22 800 cm^{-1} to $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$, $b_2 \rightarrow e\pi^*$ and $b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ transitions, respectively. The bands observed in the region 10 700–10 800, 15 200–16 000 and 18 200–18 700 cm^{-1} in the present bimetallic compounds are accordingly assigned to $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$, $b_2 \rightarrow e\pi^*$ and $b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$, respectively, assuming tetragonal pyramidal geometry (C_{4v} symmetry) around oxovanadium(II) ion.

Ir spectra: The bands occurring in the ir spectra of $\text{MM}'(\text{Etxant})_4$ at 1 190–1 260 and 1 005–1 030 cm^{-1} are assigned^{1,2} to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ modes, respectively. The number and positions of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ indicate uninegative bidentate¹¹ behaviour of xanthate ion in the above complexes. In oxovanadium(II) complexes the V=O stretching frequency occurs at 950–990 cm^{-1} which is the usual range for such complexes⁶. The ir spectra of uranyl complexes show bands at 890–905 cm^{-1} due to asymmetric vibration of linear O—U—O group¹². In all the complexes the bands occurring below 400 cm^{-1} have been tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ modes^{13,14}, the lower one may be due to Ag—S, Tl—S, Pb—S or U—S and the higher one due to V—S, Zn—S or Cd—S stretching modes, respectively.

Based on analytical data and physicochemical studies polymeric structures are proposed for the complexes.

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Equilibrium Study of the Complex Formation of some Bivalent Metal Ions with *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-aminobiphenyl and *N*-(2-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine

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THE literature survey reveals that no work on the interaction of the Schiff base ligands *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-2-aminobiphenyl (hereafter, AH) and *N*-(2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-naphthylamine (hereafter, BH) with metal ions in solution has been reported so far. The present investigation is aimed at determination of stability constants of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Mg^{II} complexes with the ligands AH and BH in 75% (v/v) dioxan—water medium having a constant ionic strength 0.1 *M* at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Experimental

The ligands AH and BH were synthesised¹ by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with 2-aminobiphenyl and 1-naphthylamine, respectively, in ethanol. The products were purified by repeated crystallisation from ethanol, and the purity was tested by tlc and elemental analysis: AH, m.p. 98° (Found: C, 80.00; H, 5.72; N, 4.64. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for: C, 79.21; H, 5.61; N, 4.62%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 600 (OH) and 1 605 cm^{-1} (C=N); BH, m.p. 91° (Found: C, 78.01; H, 5.53; N, 5.10. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for: C, 77.98; H, 5.42; N, 5.53%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 600 (OH) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

A Elico LI-15 pH meter (accuracy 0.1 pH) was employed for pH determination. The pH meter was calibrated by using aqueous buffer solutions of 0.05 *M* potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4.019 at 30°) and 0.01 *M* borax (pH 9.18 at 30°).

The relation between the pH meter reading (*B*) in water—dioxan medium and stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration of the same has been studied by Van Uitert and Haas² in mixtures of different compositions at different ionic strengths, and it has been shown that

$$-\log H = B + \log f + \log U^0 H$$

where, *f* is the activity coefficient of the hydrogen ions in the solvent mixture under consideration at the same temperature and ionic strength, and $U^0 H$ is the correction factor of zero ionic strength, which depends upon the composition of the solvent and temperature only.

The metal perchlorate solutions were standardised by EDTA methods³. Procedure for pH-metric

titration was the same as described in earlier communication⁴. The representative pH titration curves is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of AH.

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES WITH AH AND BH

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°, Dioxan-water = 3 : 1, μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Constant	AH	BH
$pK_{LH_2}^H$	—	1.9
pK_{LH}^H	9.90	10.0
$\log K_{CuL}^{Cu}$	9.46	9.64
$\log K_{CuL_2}^{Cu}$	8.32	8.27
$\log K_{NiL}^{Ni}$	6.16	6.45
$\log K_{CoL}^{Co}$	6.08	5.97
$\log K_{ZnL}^{Zn}$	6.07	6.15
$\log K_{CdL}^{Cd}$	5.08	5.33
$\log K_{MgL}^{Mg}$	4.27	4.37

Limits of error ± 0.04 - 0.25.

Results and Discussion

Formation functions $\bar{n}_A$ (average number of H⁺ bound to ligand A⁻ or B⁻), $\bar{n}$ (average number of

ligand A⁻ or B⁻ bound to M(II) ions) and pL (where, $[L]$ = equilibrium concentration of free ligand A⁻ and B⁻) were calculated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti using the pH titration curves⁵ (Fig. 1). The pK_{LH}^H and $pK_{LH_2}^H$ values of the ligands ($LH_2 = AH_2$ and BH_2) were evaluated by Bjerrum's half-integral method⁹. These values were further refined by the method of linear plots⁶. The formation curves of metal ligand systems were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ vs pL . The values of $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{ML_2}^M$ were determined by half integral method and were further refined by the method of least-squares⁷. The results are stated in Table 1. The equilibrium constants K_{LH}^H corresponds to deprotonation of phenolic OH group of the ligands. Lower pK_{LH}^H value of AH is probably due to the steric effect.

The stability constants of complexes of bivalent metal ions with the ligands AH and BH are in good agreement with Irving-Williams order⁸.

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Evaluation of Excess Internal Pressure and Excess Free Length in Ternary Liquid Mixtures

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INTERACTION studies in binary liquid mixtures in the light of excess functions have been a matter of sufficient interest during the last few decades^{1,2}. The free length concept of Jacobson has been used by various workers to study the intermolecular interaction in binary liquid mixtures³. Kaulgud⁴ and Naidu and Krishnan⁵ have evaluated intermolecular free length employing thermodynamic approach, while Schaffs⁶ applied ultrasonic approach to evaluate intermolecular free length.